

Two-step spin crossover in Hofmann-type coordination polymers

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ABSTRACT: Two 2D Hofmann-type complexes of composition $[\text{Fe}(\text{Phpz})_2\{\text{M}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]$ (where *Phpz* = 2-phenylpyrazine; M = Ag, Au) have been synthesized and their spin-crossover (SCO) behavior has been thoroughly characterized. Single crystal X-ray analysis reveals that these complexes contain a crystallographically unique Fe(II) center surrounded by two axial 2-phenylpyrazine ligands and four equatorial cyanide $[\text{M}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ bridges. It is shown that using of a ligand with two aromatic rings, an advanced system of weak supramolecular interactions (metal-metal, C–H···M and $\pi\cdots\pi$ stacking contacts) is realized. This ensures additional stabilization of the structures and the absence of a solvent accessible voids due to dense packing. Both complexes are characterized by highly reproducible two-step SCO behavior, as revealed by different techniques (SQUID magnetometry, optical microscopy, etc.). Research shows the exceptional role of the presence of various supramolecular interactions in the structure and the influence of the bulky substituent in the ligand on SCO behavior. Moreover, the perspective of substituted pyrazines for the design of new switchable materials is supported by this work.

■ INTRODUCTION

Coordination compounds of the mid-first-row transition metals with nitrogen-containing ligands keep their relevance among researchers for many years because of the versatility of their magnetic behavior. This includes unique ability of these systems to reversibly switch between high-spin (HS) and low-spin (LS) electronic states of the central metal ion under the influence of external factors (temperature, pressure, guest molecule insertion, etc.). This phenomenon is usually referred as spin crossover (SCO).¹⁻⁵ The variety of properties affected by the spin transition defines a wide

range of proposed practical applications for these materials: thermochromic elements, nano-sized chemical memory units, chemical sensors, microwave switches, microelectronic devices, magneto-optical materials etc..⁶⁻¹⁶ Multi-step SCO (with two or more steps) are interesting for understanding the nature of short-range interactions (steric and electronic), and longer-range packing effects on the cooperativity. In addition, understanding the nature of multi-step SCO may help in developing more advanced functional materials. The multi-step SCO can be caused by two different structural reasons: the presence of non-equivalent metal centers which undergo SCO at different temperatures¹⁷⁻²¹ and the symmetry breaking within the structure caused by a change in the space group or various host-host/host-guest interactions which stabilize intermediate states between purely HS and LS states.²²⁻²⁹ It is worth mentioning a number of cases when the nature of the two-step SCO remains enigmatic since the complexes contain one crystallographically unique Fe(II) center at all temperatures, and the values of all structural parameters (including bond lengths and angles) have an "average" HS/LS character at the plateau.³⁰⁻³²

To date, quite a few examples of materials showing multi-step SCO behavior are known.^{17-27,30-46} There are several examples of three-,³⁷⁻³⁹ four-,^{23,25,26,40-45} six/five-²⁷ and even an example of a seven/eight-step⁴⁶ spin transition. It should be noted that significant number of such systems are Hofmann clathrate analogues, especially with dicyanometallic $[M(CN)_2]^-$ ($M = Ag, Au$) fragments and pyridine derivatives (ranging from simple monosubstituted to more complicated ligand systems).^{2,8} In these complexes Fe(II) ions have a pseudo-octahedral coordination environment $[FeN_6]$ with two axial azine ligands and four dicyanometallic $[M(CN)_2]^-$ fragments that occupy equatorial positions. Significant advances in the production of multi-step 3D SCO systems have been achieved by Tong et al.^{23,25,26,32,46,47} They showed that the use of various long bent pillaring ligand systems, as well as the introduction of different guest molecules, leads to distortions in

coordination framework (including due to various interactions host-guest), which leads to the symmetry breaking required for a multi-step SCO.

Some Hofmann clathrate analogues based on fused bicyclic azine ligands also display multi-step SCO behavior. For example, the use of isoquinoline ligand (*isoq*) makes it possible to obtain a complex of composition $[\text{Fe}(\textit{isoq})_2\{\text{Au}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]$, which exhibits tristability for its spin states in a wide temperature range and contains three inequivalent Fe(II) sites.³⁴ Using 2,6-naphthyridine (*2,6-naphthy*), it is possible to obtain both a complex with a relatively abrupt two-step SCO in the temperature range 150–215 K, $[\text{Fe}(\textit{2,6-naphthy})\{\text{Ag}(\text{CN})_2\}\{\text{Ag}_2(\text{CN})_3\}]$, and a complex with an incomplete one-step SCO around 166 K, $[\text{Fe}(\textit{2,6-naphthy})\{\text{Au}(\text{CN})_2\}_2] \cdot 0,5\text{PhNO}_2$.⁴⁸ Whereas the use of 1,6-naphthyridine (*1,6-naphthy*) as a ligand (structural isomer of *2,6-naphthy*) leads to a complex of the composition $[\text{Fe}(\textit{1,6-naphthy})_2(\text{Ag}(\text{CN})_2)_2]$, which exhibits hysteretic SCO behavior centered at room temperature.⁴⁹

Moreover, functionalization of the pyrazine (*pz*) ligand and its derivatives can also lead to multi-step SCO materials.⁵⁰ Using 2-fluoropyrazine (*Fpz*) the SCO compound of composition $[\text{Fe}(\textit{Fpz})\{\text{Au}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]$ could be obtained, and it displays a hysteretic SCO characterized by small plateaus upon the HS \rightarrow LS (at 91%) and LS \rightarrow HS (at 23%) transformations.⁵¹ Another interesting example is the complex $[\text{Fe}(\textit{Mepz})\{\text{Au}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]$ (*Mepz* = 2-methylpyrazine) that undergoes an incomplete stepped SCO with $T_{c1} = 170$ K and $T_{c2} = 308$ K. Supposedly, this may be related to the existence of three Fe types due to *Mepz* ligand disorder. In contrast, the silver-containing analogue remains HS during the whole temperature range.⁵²

The fact that the type and size of the substituent in the pyrazine ring have significant influences on SCO characteristics of iron(II) complexes based on it prompts the use of other 2-substituted pyrazines for the design of new switchable materials. Previous studies, as mentioned above,

included the use of halogens (F, Cl, I), alkyl (Me) and amino groups as substituents.^{50–53} Therefore, to fully comprehend the effect of the substituent on SCO, as well as to expand the library of SCO complexes based on 2-substituted pyrazines, it was decided to use the aromatic substituent – phenyl. The presence of two aromatic rings in 2-phenylpyrazine theoretically implies the doubled number of $\pi\cdots\pi$ interactions. It was expected to afford enhanced cooperativity of SCO systems, as was observed for a similar example from the family of SCO complexes based on substituted pyridines.⁵⁴

Here we report on the synthesis and comparative analysis of SCO properties of two 2D Hofmann-like frameworks with 2-phenylpyrazine (*Phpz*) of composition $[\text{Fe}(\text{Phpz})_2\{\text{M}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]$ (where M = Ag, Au).

■ EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials and General Procedures. All chemicals were purchased from commercial suppliers and used without further purification. Anhydrous potassium dicyanoaurate ($\text{K}[\text{Au}(\text{CN})_2]$) and anhydrous potassium dicyanoargentate ($\text{K}[\text{Ag}(\text{CN})_2]$) were purchased from commercial sources (Sigma Aldrich). 2-Phenylpyrazine (*Phpz*) and methanol (MeOH) were provided by UkrOrgSyntez Ltd. Iron(II) *p*-toluenesulfonate hexahydrate ($\text{Fe}(\text{OTs})_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was obtained as previously described by Coucouvanis.⁵⁵

Synthesis. Bulk polycrystalline forms of **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz** were obtained by mixing alcohol solutions of $\text{Fe}(\text{OTs})_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.05 mmol in 0.25 mL of MeOH) and *Phpz* (0.20 mmol in 0.35 mL of MeOH), followed by the addition of an aqueous solution of $\text{K}[\text{M}(\text{CN})_2]$ (M = Ag, Au) (0.10 mmol in 0.15 mL of H_2O). A yellow precipitate was removed by centrifugation, washed with MeOH and dried in air for 1 hour. Yields: 86.9% (**AgPhpz**), 47.8% (**AuPhpz**). Elemental Analysis of $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{16}\text{Ag}_2\text{FeN}_8$ (**AgPhpz**): calcd. C, 41.90; H, 2.34; N, 16.29; found C, 41.81; H, 2.40; N,

16.18%. FT-IR (cm^{-1}): 2153(m), 1523(w), 1469(m), 1447(m), 1401(m), 1302(w), 1188(w), 1149(s), 1125(s), 1085(m), 1046(w), 1025(m), 1012(w), 920(w), 852(m), 769(s), 739(w), 691(s), 662(w), 618(s), 568(s), 473(w), 428(s), 419(s), 406(s). Elemental Analysis of $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{16}\text{Au}_2\text{FeN}_8$ (**AuPhpz**): calcd. C, 33.28; H, 1.86; N, 12.94; found C, 33.43; H, 2.04; N, 12.91%. FT-IR (cm^{-1}): 2174(s), 1524(w), 1470(m), 1448(s), 1402(m), 1303(m), 1189(w), 1150(s), 1123(m), 1085(s), 1046(m), 1026(s), 1014(w), 919(w), 851(s), 768(s), 745(m), 695(s), 687(s), 662(m), 617(m), 568(s), 476(m), 426(s), 407(w). Elemental analyses (CHN) were performed with a Vario Micro Cube (Elementar) CHNOS elemental analyzer.

Single crystals of **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz** were grown via a slow diffusion method within three layers in a 5 mL tube. 0.25 mL of an aqueous solution of $\text{K}[\text{M}(\text{CN})_2]$ ($\text{M} = \text{Ag}, \text{Au}$) (0.05 mmol) was poured on the bottom of the tube. Then 2.5 mL of a water-methanol mixture (1:1) was gently layered on top. The third layer was a solution (0.5 mL) of $\text{Fe}(\text{OTs})_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.025 mmol) and *Phpz* (0.10 mmol) in MeOH. Yellow crystals were obtained in the second layer after 2 weeks. Crystals were kept under the mother solution prior to the subsequent measurements. It should be noted that it is important to adhere to the proportions and mixing sequence, since for **AuPhpz** there is a certain probability of the production of a coordination compound $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_2(\text{Phpz})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2][\text{Au}(\text{CN})_2]$.⁵⁶

X-ray Diffraction. Single-crystal X-ray diffraction data were collected on Oxford-Diffraction XCALIBUR Eos CCD diffractometer with graphite-monochromated Mo- $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation at 293, 147, 110 K (for **AgPhpz**) and at 296, 200, 112 K (for **AuPhpz**). The unit cell determination and data integration were carried out using the CrysAlisPro package from Oxford Diffraction. Multi-scan correction for absorption was applied. The structures were solved with ShelXT program using intrinsic phasing method and refined by full-matrix least-squares method on F^2 with ShelXL.^{57,58}

Olex2 was used as an interface to the ShelX programs.⁵⁹ Non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Aromatic hydrogen atoms were geometrically fixed and refined using a riding model. Detailed crystallographic data for **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz** are provided in the Supporting Information (SI, Crystallographic Tables). Specific details of each refinement are given in the crystallographic information files (CIF-files). The distortion parameters (Σ) were calculated using the OctaDist tool.⁶⁰

Magnetic measurements. Temperature-dependent magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out using a MPMS3 SQUID magnetometer (Quantum Design Inc., San Diego, CA, USA) in DC mode, under a DC magnetic field of 1000 Oe, with a heating/cooling rate of 2 K min⁻¹, in the temperature region 50–250 K for **AgPhpz** and 100–300 K for **AuPhpz**. These regions were selected based on the preliminary optical experiments. **AgPhpz** (13.49 mg) or **AuPhpz** (5.16 mg) (bulk polycrystalline form) was loaded into a gelatin cap, which was placed in a plastic straw and then inserted in SQUID chamber at room temperature. Sample's position was identified at room temperature. All data were corrected for the diamagnetic contributions of the cap and the compound (estimated from Pascal's constants).⁶¹

Mössbauer measurements. The Mössbauer spectra for **AgPhpz** sample were measured at 290, 147 and 90 K using a MC-1104E Mössbauer spectrometer equipped with a liquid nitrogen cryostat. A ⁵⁷Co source embedded in a Cr matrix and activity of about 10 mCi was used. Fitting of the experimental data was performed with OriginPro software. All isomer shift values are relative to sodium nitroprusside at room temperature with the next recalculation relative to α -Fe. Mössbauer spectra for **AuPhpz** sample were measured at 293, 200 and 90 K using a constant acceleration Mössbauer spectrometer equipped with a liquid nitrogen cryostat. A ⁵⁷Co source embedded in a

Rh matrix and activity of ~ 25 mCi was used. Fitting of the experimental data was performed with OriginPro software. All isomer shifts are given relatively to iron metal at room temperature.

Raman spectroscopy. Raman spectra were recorded using Horiba Scientific LabRam HR Evolution spectrometer in the $25\text{--}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ frequency range. Green laser with 1% ND filter was used for Raman excitation at 532 nm. Temperature control was realized using Linkam THMS 600 cryostat. The following parameters were used: acquisition time 100 s; 3 accumulations; grating 600 gr/mm.

FT-IR spectroscopy. IR spectra were recorded with a Spectrum Two spectrometer (PerkinElmer Inc., Waltham, MA, USA) in attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode in ambient conditions. Spectra were recorded at 4 cm^{-1} resolutions. Wavelength range: $3500\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Variable temperature IR measurements were performed in the $625\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral range in transmittance mode on a Nicolet Nexus 470 spectrometer. Samples of **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz** were homogenized in liquid paraffin and placed between two KBr pellets. IR spectra were collected with vacuumized Specac cryo-cell cooled with liquid nitrogen in the temperature range 100–290 K. Temperature control was realized using Specac Variable Temperature Cell Controller.

Optical measurements. The system for monitoring the SCO by changing the intensity of the reflected light for bulk polycrystalline forms of both complexes consisted of an optical microscope Optica SZM-1 equipped with the optical camera Sigeta UCMOS 1300. The system for monitoring the SCO by changing the intensity of the transmitted light for single crystals of both complexes consisted of an optical microscope MICROMed XS-8530 equipped with a $\times 10$ long working-distance objective (numerical aperture, NA = 0.25) and a CCD MICROMed camera 5.0 mPix. The sample temperature was controlled with a Linkam optical cryostat DSC600. Cooling/heating rates were 0.5, 1, 5 and 10 K min^{-1} . Before starting experiment, we purged of the air from the stage

chamber with dry nitrogen. Photographs were taken automatically using ToupView software (for bulk polycrystalline forms) and Plugable Digital Viewer v3.1.07 software (for single crystals). Image processing was performed using ImageJ software.

■ RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

X-ray diffraction. To establish the crystal structure of the title compounds, single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis was carried out. The crystallographic data and structure refinements for complexes $[\text{Fe}(\text{Phpz})_2\{\text{Ag}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]$ (**AgPhpz**) and $[\text{Fe}(\text{Phpz})_2\{\text{Au}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]$ (**AuPhpz**) are summarized in Tables S4-S40 (see SI). Moreover, bulk polycrystalline forms of the complexes were examined using PXRD diffraction. This ancillary experiment confirmed the correspondence between of the structures of bulk polycrystalline forms and crystals for each complex. Thermal treatment (heating to 380 K) does not affect the structures as revealed by PXRD (Fig. S1-S3).

The crystal structure determination of **AgPhpz** was performed at 110 (LS), 293 (HS) and 147 K (plateau region corresponding to the HS/LS state). It was found that **AgPhpz** crystallizes in the monoclinic $P2_1/n$ space group, which is preserved at all temperatures. The structure contains a crystallographically unique Fe(II) center surrounded by two axial 2-phenylpyrazine ligands and four equatorial N-bound cyanide groups from two pairs of crystallographically independent $[\text{Ag}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ bridges. The key structural fragment is shown in Figure 1a. The $[\text{Ag}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ units bridge the Fe(II) ion parallel to the bc plane forming 2D $[\text{Fe}\{\text{Ag}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]_\infty$ layers with (4,4)-net topology (Fig. 1b). $[\text{Ag}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ bridges have an almost linear geometry of C–Ag–C moieties, e.g. the corresponding angles are $171.5(4)$ – $172.5(4)^\circ$ (at 293 K), $172.54(10)$ – $172.91(10)^\circ$ (at 147 K) and $171.9(4)$ – $174.4(3)^\circ$ (at 110 K).

Figure 1. Crystal structure of **AgPhpz**: a) Representation of a key fragment of **AgPhpz**. Atom code: Fe (brown), Ag (green), N (blue), C (gray). Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. b) View of the 2D $[\text{Fe}\{\text{Ag}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]_\infty$ layers with (4,4)-net topology. Double-layered structure of **AgPhpz** supported by argentophilic $\text{Ag}\cdots\text{Ag}$ interactions (turquoise dash lines).

At 293 K, the average $\langle\text{Fe}-\text{N}\rangle$ bond length is 2.181(8) Å corresponding to the HS state of Fe(II) ions. At 147 K and 110 K, they are 2.071(2) and 1.970(8) Å, respectively, i.e., the average $\langle\text{Fe}-\text{N}\rangle$ bond lengths are shorter by 0.110 and 0.211 Å comparing to the HS form indicating the complete SCO achieved at 110 K. The average axial $\text{Fe}-\text{N}_{\text{Phpz}}$ bond lengths are larger than the equatorial $\text{Fe}-\text{N}_{\text{CN}}$ by 0.038 Å at 293 K and by 0.021 Å at 110 K. Moreover, the SCO provokes a gradual decrease of the polyhedral volume of FeN_6 from 13.801 Å³ (293 K) to 10.177 Å³ (110 K) with an intermediate value of 11.834 Å³ at 147 K. The total change of the volume of the unit cell is 9.1%. At 293 K, the distortion parameter (Σ , the sum of deviations of the 12 “*cis*” N–Fe–N angles from 90°) is equal to 19.33°, while the Σ values of other two states are almost the same: 16.91° at 147 K and 16.88° at 110 K. Thus, as expected, the geometry around the coordination center in the HS

state is more distorted than in the HS/LS and LS states. Selected angles and bond lengths are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Selected angles and bond lengths for **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz**.

	AgPhpz			AuPhpz		
T (K)	293	147	110	296	200	112
Spin state	HS	HS/LS	LS	HS	HS/LS	LS
<Fe–N>_{average} (Å)	2.181(8)	2.071(2)	1.970(8)	2.165(12)	2.059(10)	1.967(14)
<Fe–N>_{Phpz} (Å)	2.206(9)	2.090(2)	1.984(8)	2.226(12)	2.101(9)	1.998(14)
<Fe–N>_{CN} (Å)	2.168(8)	2.062(2)	1.963(8)	2.135(11)	2.038(10)	1.952(12)
V_{oct}(FeN₆) (Å³)	13.801	11.834	10.177	13.508	11.625	10.140
Σ (°)	19.33	16.91	16.88	10.55	13.70	13.62
∠<C–M–C> (°)	172.0(4)	172.7(1)	173.2(4)	178.8(6)	179.5(5)	179.6(6)
∠<Fe–N≡C> (°)	172.8(8)	173.4(2)	174.4(7)	168.7(12)	171.4(10)	172.2(12)

As in other Hofmann-type SCO complexes with [Ag(CN)₂][−] bridges, argentophilic Ag⋯Ag interactions are observed in **AgPhpz** (Fig. 1b). At 293 K, the length of Ag⋯Ag contacts is 3.0865(13) Å. Temperature decrease leads to the shortening of the Ag⋯Ag contacts, and they are 3.0617(3) Å (at 147 K) and 3.0361(10) Å (at 110 K). Moreover, the distance between two adjacent noninteracting layers (Fe1 to Ag2 distance) is reduced from 7.866(2) Å at 293 K to 7.7691(5) Å at 147 K and 7.704(2) Å at 110 K.

In addition, **AgPhpz** is characterized by a dense packing also due to various other supramolecular interactions. Selected parameters of supramolecular contacts are given in Table 2. The presence of more than one aromatic ring in the azine ligand leads to the fact that the packing of the 2-phenylpyrazine rings is held by different kinds of π⋯π stacking interactions (Fig. 2b).

There are two sets of short π -stacking with parallel-displaced (offset) conformation and two sets with T-shaped conformation (C–H $\cdots\pi$ interaction). As a result, such an advanced system of weak π -contacts leads to additional stabilization of the structure and the absence of a solvent accessible voids due to dense packing. ‘Edge-to-face’ contacts (C–H $\cdots\pi$ interaction) deserve more attention since are rarely found in Hofmann clathrates.^{25,26} At 293 K, C13–H13 \cdots C’_{ring} / C15–H15 \cdots C’_{ring} distances are 2.964(4) / 3.142(5) Å (where C’_{ring} is the centroid of C19C20C21C22C23C24 aromatic ring; C’’_{ring} is the centroid of N6C15C16N8C17C18 aromatic ring). They are 2.8718(10) / 3.0587(10) Å at 147 K and 2.791(4) / 2.9522(2) Å at 110 K. The offset $\pi\cdots\pi$ interactions are characterized by centroid-centroid distances of 3.589(6)–3.610(6) Å in the HS state, 3.5261(10)–3.5654(10) Å in the HS/LS state and 3.509(4)–3.545(4) Å in the LS state. These distances lie at the middle of the typical distance range for such supramolecular interactions (from 3.3 to 3.8 Å).^{62,63} It should also be noted the presence of weak intermolecular C–H \cdots Ag interactions (Fig. 2a). Since systems with this type of contacts (C–H \cdots M, where M = metal) play an important role in catalysis due to their possible involvement in C–H bond activation.⁶⁴

Figure 2. a) Supramolecular packing of **AgPhpz** via Ag...Ag (green dash lines) and C-H...M (pink and red dash lines) interactions. b) Supramolecular packing of **AgPhpz** via offset (green and red dash lines) and C-H... π (orange and yellow dash lines) π -contacts.

The compound **AuPhpz** crystallizes in the triclinic space group $P\bar{1}$ with two $[\text{Fe}(\text{Phpz})_2\{\text{Au}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]$ formula units per cell. **AuPhpz** contains only one crystallographically independent Fe(II) atom with the coordination environment of an elongated pseudo-octahedron $[\text{FeN}_6]$ similar to **AgPhpz**. Each Fe(II) center binds four cyanide groups in ab plane and two axially coordinated crystallographic non-equivalent *Phpz* ligands. Two crystallographically distinct $[\text{Au}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ bridges display virtually linear geometry. C–Au–C angles are $178.5(6)$ – $179.0(5)$, $179.2(5)$ – $179.7(4)$ and $179.6(5)$ ° at 296 K, 200 K and 112 K, respectively.

At 296 K, the average $\langle \text{Fe-N} \rangle$ bond length is 2.165(12) Å that corresponds to the HS state of Fe(II) site. At 200 K and 112 K they are 2.059(10) and 1.967(14) Å, respectively. The average $\langle \text{Fe-N} \rangle$ bond lengths are shorter by 0.106 Å (200 K) and 0.198 Å (112 K) comparing to HS form, clearly indicating a complete SCO achieved at 112 K. Like for **AgPhpz**, the average axial bond length $\text{Fe-N}_{\text{phpz}}$ in **AuPhpz** is always larger than the equatorial Fe-N_{CN} . The value of the polyhedral volume of FeN_6 drops from 13.508 Å³ (296 K) to 10.140 Å³ (112 K) with an intermediate value of 11.625 Å³ at 200 K. The total change of the volume of the unit cell is 8.0%. It should be noted that the distortion parameter (Σ) value in **AuPhpz** increases with cooling: from 10.55° at 296 K (HS) to 13.70° at 200 K (HS/LS) and 13.62° at 112 K (LS). Thus, contrary to **AgPhpz**, the geometry around the coordination center in **AuPhpz** is the most distorted in the LS and HS/LS states. A similar behavior of Σ changes has already been reported for SCO analogues and other materials.^{23,25,32,34,43,65}

An important structural feature of **AuPhpz** is the presence of strong aurophilic $\text{Au}\cdots\text{Au}$ interactions that support bilayer networks (Fig. 3a). At 296 K, the length of $\text{Au}\cdots\text{Au}$ contacts is 3.1072(8) Å. Temperature decrease leads to the shortening of the $\text{Au}\cdots\text{Au}$ contacts, and they are 3.0701(8) Å (at 200 K) and 3.0465(10) Å (at 112 K). Moreover, the distance between two adjacent noninteracting layers (Fe1 to Au2 distance) is reduced from 9.683(2) Å at 296 K to 9.584(2) Å at 147 K and 9.545(2) Å at 112 K. Also noteworthy is the lack of $\text{C-H}\cdots\text{Au}$ contacts in **AuPhpz**. Due to this, the **AuPhpz** structure is characterized by a larger than in **AgPhpz** distance between two adjacent noninteracting layers (Fe1 to M2) and the presence of small solvent accessible voids. The Olex2 software shows a total solvent accessible volume/cell of 7.6% (101.9 Å³) at 296 K, 5.2% (65.9 Å³) at 200 K and 4.3% (53.7 Å³) at 112 K.

Table 2. Selected parameters of supramolecular contacts.

	AgPhpz			AuPhpz		
T (K)	293	147	110	296	200	112
Spin state	HS	HS/LS	LS	HS	HS/LS	LS
	Ag...Ag interaction			Au...Au interaction		
M...M (Å)	3.0865(13)	3.0617(3)	3.0361(10)	3.1072(8)	3.0701(8)	3.0465(10)
offset π...π interactions						
C_{ring}-C'_{ring} (Å)	3.589(6)	3.5261(10)	3.509(4)	-	-	-
C''_{ring}-C'''_{ring} (Å)	3.610(6)	3.5654(10)	3.545(4)	-	-	-
C'_{ring}-C''_{ring} (Å)	-	-	-	3.666(11)	3.587(4)	3.499(2)
C-H...π interactions						
C13-H13...C''_{ring} (Å)	2.964(4)	2.8718(10)	2.791(4)	-	-	-
\angleC13-H13...C''_{ring} (°)	136.3(9)	135.7(2)	136.0(3)	-	-	-
C15-H15...C'_{ring} (Å)	3.142(5)	3.0587(10)	2.9522(2)	-	-	-
\angleC15-H15...C'_{ring} (°)	153.6(7)	152.9(2)	150.8(5)	-	-	-
C16-H16...C'''_{ring} (Å)	-	-	-	2.650(4)	2.6014(2)	2.546(6)
\angleC16-H16...C'''_{ring} (°)	-	-	-	142.7(12)	144.3(7)	146.4(2)
C-H...M interactions						
C22-H22...Ag1 (Å)	2.6469(10)	2.6048(2)	2.5023(7)	-	-	-
C22...Ag1 (Å)	3.229(13)	3.142(2)	3.061(6)	-	-	-
\angleC22-H22...Ag1 (°)	121.2(8)	117.27(13)	117.6(4)	-	-	-
C20-H20...Ag2 (Å)	2.6697(10)	2.6392(3)	2.5662(7)	-	-	-
C20...Ag2 (Å)	3.486(11)	3.460(2)	3.415(5)	-	-	-
\angleC20-H20...Ag2 (°)	146.9(7)	147.49(15)	148.8(3)	-	-	-

where C_{ring} is the centroid of the aromatic ring (C_{ring}: N5C5H6N7C7C8;

C'_{ring}: C19C20C21C22C23C24; C''_{ring}: N6C15C16N8C17C18; C'''_{ring}: C9C10C11C12C13C14)

Like for **AgPhpz**, additional stabilization of **AuPhpz** structure is realized via short $\pi\cdots\pi$ stacking interactions (Fig. 3b). There are π -stacking with parallel-displaced (offset) and T-shaped (C–H $\cdots\pi$ interaction) conformations. It should be noted that the offset $\pi\cdots\pi$ contact is observed only in one of the two *Phpz* ligands (between aromatic rings N6C15C16N8C17C18 and C19C20C21C22C23C24) with the centroid \cdots centroid distance of 3.666(11) Å in the HS state, 3.587(4) Å in the HS/LS state and 3.499(2) Å in the LS state. Another *Phpz* ligand forms only C–H $\cdots\pi$ interactions (Fig. 3b). Selected parameters of supramolecular contacts are given in Table 2.

Figure 3. Crystal structure of **AuPhpz**: a) View of the 2D $[\text{Fe}\{\text{Au}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]_\infty$ layers with (4,4)-net topology. Double-layered structure of **AuPhpz** supported by aurophilic $\text{Au}\cdots\text{Au}$ interactions (green dash lines). b) Supramolecular packing of **AuPhpz** via offset (red) and C–H $\cdots\pi$ (orange) π -contacts.

Comparing architectures of **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz**, it is worth noting that both complexes at the plateau temperature have only one crystallographically independent Fe(II) center, and the values of all structural parameters (including bond lengths and angles) have an "average" HS/LS character. Such behavior has already been observed for similar systems.^{31,32} Moreover, due to the advanced system of supramolecular interactions both complexes do not contain guest molecules, although **AuPhpz** has small solvent accessible voids. Another distinctive feature of both complexes is the different behavior of structural changes in the coordination environment of the Fe(II) site upon SCO (the distortion parameter, Σ). The superposition of the HS and LS structures for both complexes show virtually ideal overlay of all structural fragments (Fig. S13-S18). Some minor displacements of atoms are mainly caused by a change in the Fe–N bond lengths by ~ 0.2 Å upon SCO. Comparison of the HS and LS structures with the HS/LS structure for **AgPhpz** shows some differences beyond the coordination sphere (contrary to **AuPhpz**) (Fig. S14-S15). Thus, both distortion of cyanide $[\text{Ag}(\text{CN})_2]^-$ bridges lying in the *bc* plane and a slight torsion of the 2-phenylpyrazine ligand are observed.

Magnetic measurements. The electronic reorganization in the Fe(II) ion during SCO causes a sharp change of magnetic susceptibility (χ_M). Thus, the temperature dependence of χ_M for bulk polycrystalline forms of complexes **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz** were measured by superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) in cooling and heating regimes (Fig. 4).

Complex **AgPhpz** undergoes a gradual two-step transition over the temperature range ~ 100 K (Fig. 4a) like for similar silver-containing SCO systems.^{32,36,44} The $\chi_M T$ value is $3.53 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ K mol}^{-1}$ at 273 K, $1.86 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ K mol}^{-1}$ at 147 K, and $0.23 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ K mol}^{-1}$ at 50 K, which allows to roughly estimate the completeness of the transition 0%, 47%, and 94%, respectively. This corroborates with the complete stepped transformation of Fe(II) ion from the HS state ($S = 2$, paramagnetic) to

LS state ($S = 0$, diamagnetic). The transition temperatures are 175 (T_{c1}) and 125 K (T_{c2}) with a narrow pseudo-plateau appearing between 145 and 149 K. In the subsequent heating mode, these parameters are completely retained, and the transition curve reproduces the curve in cooling regime. It was found that **AgPhpz** is characterized by transition temperatures similar to silver-containing SCO complexes based on pyridine-type ligands.^{33,36,44,66}

Figure 4. $\chi_M T$ vs. T plots for bulk polycrystalline forms of **AgPhpz** (a) and **AuPhpz** (b) in the selected transition area showing gradual temperature induced two-step SCO in these complexes. Derivative curves $d(\chi_M T)/dT$ are plotted.

The $\chi_{\text{M}}T$ value of **AuPhpz** is $3.06 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ K mol}^{-1}$ at 273 K, indicating the HS state of Fe(II) ion. Upon further cooling, $\chi_{\text{M}}T$ gradually decreases to $0.43 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ K mol}^{-1}$ at 100 K corresponding to the practically complete LS fraction. Two-step SCO behavior with critical temperatures of $T_{\text{c}1} = 216 \text{ K}$ and $T_{\text{c}2} = 185 \text{ K}$ is revealed by the differential $d(\chi_{\text{M}}T)/dT$ versus T plots (Fig. 4b). The $\chi_{\text{M}}T$ value at the midpoint of the pseudo-plateau is $1.80 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ K mol}^{-1}$ at 200 K, corresponding to a resultant 41% HS fraction. It should be noted that **AuPhpz** undergoes a more gradual two-step SCO (over $\sim 110 \text{ K}$) with higher transition temperatures compared to **AgPhpz**. The difference in transition temperatures can be explained by different cooperative effects in these compounds caused by slightly different set of supramolecular interactions. A nice similar example is complexes based on 4-methylpyrimidine of composition $[\text{Fe}(\text{4-methylpyrimidine})_2[\text{M}^{\text{I}}(\text{CN})_2]_2]$ (where $\text{M}^{\text{I}} = \text{Ag, Au}$), where the silver analogue has lower transition temperature comparing to the gold analogue. In that case the difference is also explained from the point of different crystal packing effects: presence of $\text{M}\cdots\text{M}$ interactions, $\text{M}\cdots\text{N}$ contacts and other structural features.^{24,67}

Because of the spin-orbit interaction, the experimental value of $\chi_{\text{M}}T$ for the HS state of both complexes is higher than one calculated based on the spin of Fe(II) and equal to $\sim 3.1\text{--}3.5 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ K mol}^{-1}$. These $\chi_{\text{M}}T$ values are typical for most Fe(II) Hofmann-like clathrates reported previously ($\sim 3.0\text{--}3.8 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ K mol}^{-1}$).^{2,8,68} A small positive magnetization at low temperature ($0.23 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ K mol}^{-1}$ (at 50 K) for **AgPhpz** and $0.43 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ K mol}^{-1}$ (at 100 K) for **AuPhpz**) is observed. Contribution of some HS Fe(II) impurities may be suspected, however their quantities are small enough that they are not seen on Mössbauer spectra (Fig. 5). A similar magnetic behavior was previously observed for different Hofmann-type coordination polymers.^{2,8,69,70}

Gradual SCO at both steps in **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz** indicates a weak cooperativity between metallic centers as compared to high-temperature hysteretic behavior of complexes based on unsubstituted pyrazine of the composition $[\text{Fe}(\text{pz})\{\text{M}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]$ ($\text{M} = \text{Ag}, \text{Au}$).^{71,72} Thus, it can be concluded that the introduction of a bulky phenyl substituent to the pyrazine ring makes azine ligand being monodentate, that in its turn affects the SCO properties of both complexes (although, there is no any straightforward explanation of the nature of two-step transitions). The phenyl group sterically blocks the nearest donor nitrogen atom of the pyrazine ligand, which is a potential axial coordination donor. This makes 2-phenylpyrazine ligand similar to pyridine-type ligands, which frequently lead to the formation of multi-step SCO complexes with transition temperatures below RT. Also, it was already shown in previous studies that some SCO complexes based on 2-substituted pyrazines exhibit low-temperature two-step transitions.^{50,51}

Because of the gradual character of SCO in both complexes, DSC is poorly suitable to monitor spin state change in these compounds. DSC peaks can be observed only at high scan rates (50-80 K min^{-1}), although the phase transition temperatures are reasonably well consistent with the temperatures found in magnetic measurements (Fig. S11-S12). Peaks for **AgPhpz** are resolved, while for **AuPhpz** only one peak is emerged.

Mössbauer measurements. SCO in **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz** was investigated by the ^{57}Fe Mössbauer spectroscopy (Fig. 5) since this method provides direct information about the spin state and oxidation state of iron atom. The Mössbauer parameters for **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz** in HS, HS/LS and LS states are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Hyperfine parameters for **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz**.

	AgPhpz	AuPhpz

T (K)	290	147	90	293	200	90
Spin state	HS	HS/LS	LS	HS	HS/LS	LS
δ (mm s⁻¹)	1.081(2)	1.19(4) (HS) 0.45(3) (LS)	0.489(2)	1.074(2)	1.142(5) (HS) 0.467(4) (LS)	0.528(2)
ΔE_Q (mm s⁻¹)	1.095(3)	1.37(8) (HS) 0.10(5) (LS)	0.104(8)	0.801(4)	1.062(10) (HS) 0.084(32) (LS)	0.119(9)
$\Gamma/2$ (mm s⁻¹)	0.121(3)	0.128(7) (HS) 0.109(7) (LS)	0.121(5)	0.158(3)	0.167(6) (HS) 0.164(11) (LS)	0.141(5)
Content (%)	100.0	48.8(21) (HS) 51.2(15) (LS)	100.0	100.0	52.5(16) (HS) 47.5(14) (LS)	100.0

At RT, the Mössbauer spectra of both **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz** consist of one doublet, the hyperfine parameters (isomer shift (δ) and quadrupole splitting (ΔE_Q)) of which indicate that all the Fe(II) sites in both complexes are in the HS state (**AgPhpz**: $\delta = 1.081(2)$ mm s⁻¹, $\Delta E_Q = 1.095(3)$ mm s⁻¹; **AuPhpz**: $\delta = 1.074(2)$ mm s⁻¹, $\Delta E_Q = 0.801(4)$ mm s⁻¹). At temperatures corresponding to the HS/LS state, the Mössbauer spectra consist of two doublets in approximately 1:1 HS/LS ratio (48.8:51.2 for **AgPhpz** and 52.5:47.5 for **AuPhpz**), which corroborates with the magnetic measurements. A further decrease in temperature down to 90 K leads to an increase in the content of LS phase to 100%, which corresponds to the complete spin state change from HS to LS. δ and ΔE_Q values are typical for Fe(II) ion in the LS state (**AgPhpz**: $\delta = 0.489(2)$ mm s⁻¹, $\Delta E_Q = 0.104(8)$ mm s⁻¹; **AuPhpz**: $\delta = 0.528(2)$ mm s⁻¹, $\Delta E_Q = 0.119(9)$ mm s⁻¹). The values of half width at half maximum ($\Gamma/2$) lie in the range of 0.12-0.17 mm s⁻¹. Thus, the hyperfine parameters of both complexes are comparable with the corresponding values for related Hofmann-type complexes with dicyanometallic $[M(CN)_2]^-$ (M = Ag, Au) fragments.³³ The values of $\Gamma/2$ suggest these are individual Fe(II) compounds and there is a single Fe(II) site in each compound.

Figure 5. Mössbauer spectra of AgPhpz and AuPhpz recorded at HS, HS/LS and LS states. Both complexes display a complete SCO. Color codes: HS - red, LS - blue.

Spectroscopic measurements.

Raman spectroscopy is a powerful (complementary to magnetometry and ^{57}Fe Mössbauer spectroscopy) method to follow SCO.^{73–80} E.g., complete disappearance of some characteristic

peaks and their appearance at different wavelengths confirm that SCO is complete in both directions (Fig. S9-S10). Figure 6 reveals the normalized intensity dependence on temperature for both complexes in the low-frequency spectral regions.

Figure 6. Raman spectra of **AgPhpz** (a) and **AuPhpz** (b) in the low-frequency spectral regions at various temperatures including temperatures corresponding to the HS, HS/LS and LS states.

It was found that the stretching mode attributed to Fe–N vibrations is shifted to the high-frequency region upon the spin state switches to the LS: from 103 to 145 cm⁻¹ ($\Delta = 42$ cm⁻¹) for **AgPhpz** and from 96 to 153 cm⁻¹ ($\Delta = 57$ cm⁻¹) for **AuPhpz**. In-plane bending vibrations of 2-phenylpyrazine are also affected by SCO. They exhibit shifts from 613 to 623 cm⁻¹ ($\Delta = 10$ cm⁻¹)

/ from 656 to 662 cm^{-1} ($\Delta = 6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) for **AgPhpz** and from 611 to 632 cm^{-1} ($\Delta = 21 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) / from 654 to 661 cm^{-1} ($\Delta = 7 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) for **AuPhpz**. Moreover, the increase of LS fraction causes a remarkable change in the intensity of the peaks at ~ 1150 and $\sim 1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which are also attributed to in-plane bending vibrations of *Phpz* (Fig. S9-S10).

Figure 7. Temperature dependence of the intensity ratio of two Raman modes for bulk polycrystalline forms of **AgPhpz** (a) and **AuPhpz** (b).

The change of the spin state of iron(II) ions was also confirmed by plotting a curve from the intensity ratio of two Raman modes vs. temperature (Fig. 7). The plotted curves correspond to those obtained from magnetic and optical measurements. The equilibrium temperatures (**AgPhpz**: $T_{c1} = 175 \text{ K}$ and $T_{c2} = 135 \text{ K}$; **AuPhpz**: $T_{c1} = 205 \text{ K}$ and $T_{c2} = 185 \text{ K}$) are well consistent with the values obtained using other techniques.

In addition, variable temperature IR measurements for both complexes were performed. A few marker bands were used to follow SCO (Fig. S5-S8). Peaks at 637 cm^{-1} and 638 cm^{-1} are characteristic only for the LS state of **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz**, respectively. The stretching peaks attributed to $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ vibrations practically do not change their position upon SCO ($\Delta \approx 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), but their intensity is affected.

Thus, all observed IR and Raman spectroscopy alterations clearly demonstrate the complete spin state change of Fe(II) and can be used as markers for monitoring SCO. The assignment of characteristic Raman and IR bands are summarized in Tables S1-S2. By comparing the vibrational modes in the HS and LS states of the obtained SCO systems with other known of Hofmann-like clathrates, it can be concluded that they follow the trend of the 2D structures with pyridine-like ligands.^{73,74,80} This is evidenced by a minor shift of the C≡N vibrational band ($\leq 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) usually observed for 2D frameworks and the typical redshift.

Optical measurements. Two-step SCO behavior in single crystals and bulk polycrystalline forms of synthesized complexes has been monitored via optical microscopy since SCO is accompanied by color change. Bulks and single crystals of **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz** are yellow at room temperature (HS), light orange in the HS/LS state and become bright orange upon cooling to 100 K (LS) (Fig. 8). Moreover, influence of the temperature scan rate on SCO behavior for different forms of these complexes has been studied. Temperature dependences of the normalized reflectance (for bulk polycrystalline forms) and normalized transmittance (for single crystals), recorded at various temperature scan rates, are given in Figure 8. The values of transition temperatures in both heating and cooling regimes are summarized in Table S3 (see SI).

Figure 8. Temperature dependent optical studies of bulk polycrystalline forms of **AgPpz** (a) and **AuPpz** (b) (normalized optical reflectance vs. temperature) and single crystals of **AgPpz** (c) and **AuPpz** (d) (normalized optical transmittance vs. temperature) at different scan rates (0.5–10 K min⁻¹). The inserted pictures show the color evolution of **AgPpz** and **AuPpz** caused by SCO.

As expected, the minor difference in sharpness of SCO for bulk polycrystalline materials and the single crystals is observed. Because both forms usually show a different degree of cooperativity in the systems (the crystals show more cooperative SCO compared to powders).^{49,81} This may lead to the appearance of kinetic effects. In our case, however, the kinetic effects are small compared to other examples in the literature; these minor changes can be as well cause by just thermalization

effects. It should also be noted that **AgPhpz** is characterized by a broader intermediate plateau (this is especially evident in case of single crystals: 21 K for **AgPhpz** vs. 5 K for **AuPhpz**), which is consistent with magnetic measurements data (Fig. 4) and can be explained by some structural differences between the complexes. **AgPhpz** is characterized by the presence of intermolecular C–H···Ag interactions and a more advanced system of weak $\pi\cdots\pi$ stacking interactions that potentially may stabilize the HS/LS state. Since optical microscopy is a semiquantitative method the HS/LS plateau does not correspond to the 50% change in the reflectance/transmittance for both **AgPhpz** and **AuPhpz** (in contrast to the magnetic curves). The reasons for this may be numerous factors: a slight increase in their opacity upon transition and just a small difference in color between HS and LS forms (yellow and orange, respectively). The collection and the treatment of images also contribute to the semiquantitative nature of the optical reflection/transmission methods used.

■ CONCLUSIONS

Two 2D Hofmann-like frameworks have been synthesized by self-assembly of Fe(II), *Phpz* and $[M(CN)_2]^-$ (M = Ag, Au) building blocks, and their SCO behavior has been thoroughly characterized. In contrast to the high-temperature hysteretic SCO complexes based on unsubstituted pyrazine (*pz*),^{71,72} both synthesized complexes exhibit the gradual two-step SCO behavior at low temperatures. The nature of the two-step SCO remains enigmatic since the complexes at the plateau temperature have only one crystallographically independent Fe(II) center, and the values of all structural parameters (including bond lengths and angles) have an "average" HS/LS character. Therefore, it is difficult to unambiguously indicate the reason of the two-step SCO behavior of these complexes; one can only assume that the presence of numerous

different supramolecular interactions such as metal-metal, C–H···M and $\pi\cdots\pi$ stacking contacts are responsible for this anti-cooperative behavior.

Thus, this research shows that slight modification of the axial ligand in cyanometallic frameworks can lead to a completely different SCO behavior. Moreover, the analysis shows the exceptional role of various supramolecular interactions in the structure and the influence of the bulky substituent in the ligand on the SCO behavior. As a result, the modification of the pyrazine ring can be used to fine-tuning the desired SCO properties for the design of new switchable materials.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. The Supporting Information (SI) contains experimental and calculated PXRD patterns, FT-IR and Raman spectra, DSC curves, images of superposition of structures **AgPhpz** and **AgPhpz**, crystal data and refinement details.

Accession Codes. CCDC 2116353-2116358 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif, or by emailing data_request@ccdc.cam.ac.uk, or by contacting The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; fax: +44 1223 336033.

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The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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Table of Contents (TOC) Graphic:

Manuscript synopsis:

Two 2D Hofmann-type coordination polymers of composition $[\text{Fe}(\text{Phpz})_2\{\text{M}(\text{CN})_2\}_2]$ (where *Phpz* = 2-phenylpyrazine; M = Ag, Au) have been synthesized and their spin-crossover (SCO) behavior has been thoroughly characterized by different techniques. Both complexes exhibit the highly reproducible two-step SCO behavior at low temperatures.